

HOW FOOD SECURITY WILL INFLUENCE TO THE ECONOMIC SECURITY OF THE COUNTRY

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Abstract. This article analyzes the current socio-economic situation of the economic security and food security of the country, as well as the study of economic, political, social factors in ensuring food security, ensuring the economic security of the country. Conclusions on the state of reforms in the field of food security and proposals on these issues are presented.

Key words: Security, food security, economic security, FAO, scarcity, price stabilization, forecast.

INTRODUCTION. Food security is achieved when all people have consistent access to sufficient, safe and nutritious food that meets their food preferences and nutritional needs to lead healthy and active lives. This is an important factor that plays a decisive role in ensuring the economic security of the country. Food security is important not only for people but also for the overall economic growth of the country. Ensuring the well-being and economic growth of any country's population is important.

Globally, the number of undernourished people in the world was around 702-828 million people in 2021, this indicator increased to 103 million people in 2019-2020, by approximately 50 million people during the COVID-19 pandemic, and by 46 million people in 2021 alone. In 2019-2022, the number of people who cannot afford to eat healthy food in the world increased by 112 million people, and now their number is 3.1 billion people¹.

The Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) has defined food security as one of the important foundations for achieving sustainable development. The article aims to study the role of food security in ensuring the country's economic security.

The world's population is constantly growing and is expected to reach 9.7 billion by 2050, putting enormous pressure on the food system. In addition, climate change, natural disasters, water scarcity and other factors can make food production and distribution difficult. Providing food to the population is important for achieving economic growth. Therefore, food safety is crucial for economic development, social stability and general well-being of the population.

The volume of agricultural products grown in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2022: Fruits and berries - 3 million tons, Grapes - 1.8 million tons, poly crops - 2.4 million tons, vegetables - 11.2 million tons, potatoes - 3.4 million tons, grain - 8 million tons².

MATERIALS AND METHODS. During the preparation of this article, research materials, results of scientific work of national and foreign researchers, as well as statistical data of the Ministry of Agriculture, Statistical Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan were used. The main materials were collected on the basis of statistical data and analyzed on the basis of available

¹ FAO, IFAD, UNICEF, WFP and WHO. 2022 The State of Food Security and Nutrition in the World 2022. Reorienting food and agriculture policies to make healthy diets more affordable. Rome, FAO. <https://doi.org/10.4060/cc0639ru>

² Data materials of the Statistical Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan - www.stat.uz

software. The obtained scientific conclusions are based on the results of scientific research.

RESULTS AND THEIR ANALYSIS. Food safety plays an important role in ensuring the country's economic security. A well-implemented food security strategy can help ensure sustainable economic growth by stabilizing food prices, encouraging investment in the agricultural sector, and promoting food exports. In addition, food security can reduce a country's dependence on imported food, thereby maintaining more foreign exchange reserves and protecting the economy from external shocks.

Agriculture is undoubtedly the main provider of food security. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, the rate of population growth is considered high, and the issue of providing food to the population is considered to be an important factor affecting the country's economic security in the future.

According to the information of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan (Fig. 1), the minimum amount of 7 types of food products important to the population is determined. In the course of the research, 7 main types of food products were studied: meat and meat products, eggs, vegetables and dairy products, potatoes, sugar, vegetable oil and other oils, as well as fruits and grapes.

Figure 1. Scientifically based medical norm of consumption of basic food products per capita in Uzbekistan, kg (pieces)³

³ Source: author's development based on data materials of the Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan

According to it, the average amount of meat and meat products for 1 person in the country for 1 year is 40.2 kg, eggs - 292 pieces, vegetables and fruits - 128.8 kg, potatoes - 54.6 kg, sugar - 19.4 kg, vegetable oil and other oils - 7.3 kg, fruit and grapes - 90.6 kg.

When the analysis of the satisfaction of the demand for the main 7 types of food products in the Republic of Uzbekistan is studied based on the data of 2022 (Table 1), the demand for 3 types of food products is sufficiently satisfied and there is a situation of excess production. Among them: vegetables and sugarcane products - 8946.8 thousand tons, potatoes - 1477.6 thousand tons, fruits and grapes - 1498.3 thousand tons of products were grown in excess of demand. Nevertheless, it was felt that there is a shortage of 4 types of food products: including meat and meat products - 234.0 thousand tons, eggs - 2382.7 million pieces, sugar - 206.3 thousand tons, vegetable oil and other oils - 146,000 tons less than the demand was produced.

Table 1

Analysis of demand satisfaction for the main 7 types of food products in the Republic of Uzbekistan (2022)

No	Types of products	Unit of measure	Current demand	Produced	Deficiency (-), excess (+)
1	Meat and meat products	thousand tons	1447,2	1213,2	-234,0
2	Egg	million units	10512	8129,3	-2382,7
3	Vegetables and poly crops	thousand tons	4636,8	13583,6	8946,8
4	Potatoes	thousand tons	1965,6	3443,2	1477,6
5	Sugar	thousand tons	698,4	492,1	-206,3
6	Vegetable oil and other oils	thousand tons	262,8	116,8	-146,0
7	Fruit and grapes	thousand tons	3261,6	4759,9	1498,3

*Source: author's development based on the Data materials of the Statistical Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan

Currently, other products besides eggs are being imported in order to meet the demand. In January-August 2022, 32,800 tons of beef worth 141.9 million dollars were imported to Uzbekistan from 9 countries⁴.

It is noted that the import of beef increased by 13.8 thousand tons compared to the same period last year.

⁴ Data materials of the Statistical Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan

In 2022, Uzbekistan imported beef from Belarus (17.1 thousand tons), Kazakhstan (11.6 thousand tons), Brazil (1.4 thousand tons), India (967 tons), Russia (791 tons) and other countries.

It is worth mentioning that in the 10 months of 2021, compared to the previous year, the import of beef increased by 7.3 thousand tons and amounted to 23.9 thousand tons. If we look at the general trend, the import of beef to Uzbekistan increased from 87 tons to 22 thousand tons from 2017 to 2020⁵.

During the research, the population of Uzbekistan was estimated to be 36.0 million people in 2023, 38.31 million people in 2030, and 45.59 million people in 2050 based on the data of the World Population Review website www.worldpopulationreview.com. According to the analysis, the population of the Republic of Uzbekistan will increase by 6.4% in 2030 compared to 2023, and by 26.6% in 2050 and will reach 45.59 million people. The rapid growth of the population at this level creates the need to increase attention to intensive production in agriculture, which is the main producer of food products, in the conditions of decreasing natural resources (land and water resources) and rapidly increasing demand.

Only these 7 types of food supply status and the amount of demand necessary for the future supply level were studied (Table 2).

Table 2

Forecast analysis of the demand for food products of the population of the Republic of Uzbekistan (2023-2050)*

№	Types of products	Unit of measure	Years		
			2023	2030	2050
			Population, million people		
			36,0	38,31	45,59
1	Meat and meat products	thousand tons	1447	1540,2	1832,8
2	Eggs	million units	10512	11187	13313
3	Vegetables and poly crops	thousand tons	4637	4934,7	5872,4
4	Potato	thousand tons	1966	2091,9	2489,4
5	Sugar	thousand tons	698	743,3	884,5
6	Vegetable oil and other oils	thousand tons	263	279,7	332,8
7	Fruit and grapes	thousand tons	3262	3471,2	4130,7

* Source: Development of the authors based on the data of the Statistical Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the website www.worldpopulationreview.com - World Population Review

⁵ <https://sputniknews.uz/20220923/O'zbekistonga-gosht-importi-bir-necha-yildan-buyon-oshmoqda---statistika-28485112.html> - Meat import to Uzbekistan has been increasing for several years - statistics. 23.09.2022

Table 2 shows that in 2023, the demand for 7 types of basic products for the population of Uzbekistan will be 1,447,000 tons of meat and meat products, 10,512 million eggs, 4,637,000 tons of vegetables and fruits, 1,966,000 tons of potatoes, and sugar. - 698 thousand tons, vegetable, oil and other types of oils - 263 thousand tons, fruits and grapes - 3262 thousand tons. These numbers will also increase by 2030 and 2050 according to the population, respectively by 2030 by 6.4%, and by 26.6% in 2050 compared to 2023. As a result, the demand for meat and meat products will reach 1,540,200 tons in 2030 and 1,832,800 tons in 2050. Population demand for food products in 2050: eggs - 13313 million pieces, vegetable and fruit products - 5872.4 thousand tons, potatoes - 2489.4 thousand tons, sugar - 884.5 thousand tons, vegetable oil and other types of oils - 332 8 thousand tons, fruit and grapes - 4130.7 thousand tons. Based on this, it is required to increase the production capacity of agribusiness entities.

As can be seen from the data of this table, by 2050, the population of our country will have a sharp increase in the demand for the main products of the primary consumer basket. This, in turn, requires the production and cultivation of more high-quality and safe products to meet people's needs. This is only in the case of our country, of course, the number of these numbers on the world scale can be quite large: in 2030 - 8.5 billion people, in 2050 - 9.7 billion people, in 2058 - 10.0 billion people⁶.

SUMMARY. The role of food security in ensuring the country's economic security cannot be overestimated. This is the main condition for economic growth and development, national security and environmental stability. Investing in a strong food security system can help improve quality of life, reduce poverty, stabilize the economy, and strengthen social and political stability. Therefore, governments, politicians and individuals must prioritize food security to ensure a prosperous and sustainable future.

Food safety plays a major role in ensuring the country's economic security. The government should realize that food security is important for economic growth and social stability and take necessary measures to ensure food security in the country.

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